

Empirical Investigation on Motivational Factors of Special Needs Students' Quest for Tertiary Education in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

Education is a key to development of individual in a holistic context. Hence, the position of the international community is to making people to have access to functional and inclusive education in respect of sex, religion, tribe and other limitations. This study was therefore carried out on empirical investigation on motivational factors of special needs students' quest for tertiary education in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used. The study population comprised special needs students. The sample size of the study was Two hundred (200) selected through a simple random sampling technique. A self-developed and structured questionnaire titled, "Empirical investigation on motivational factors of special needs students' quest for tertiary education in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria", fashioned on four likert rating scale, Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD). Three research questions were raised to guide the study. Data for the study was generated through self-structured research instruments by the researchers. The research instruments were validated by two experts in test and measurement, while its reliability was determined through test-retest method at two weeks interval. 0.67 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data generated on the research questions were analyzed, using descriptive statistics (frequency counts, simple percentages and mean). Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were made that the desire for acquiring certificate, occupational skills and economic factor were motivational factors for special needs students' participation in tertiary education in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria. Recommendations were therefore made that; adult should always availing themselves

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with available educational programmes in the commonly or society. Also, government should sensitize the adult on their need to enroll for educational programme and so on.

Keyword: Motivational factors, Educational programme, Special need students.

Background to the Study

It is truism that globally, education has been perceived as a veritable weapon to fast track a meaning human and sustainable national development, holistically. Aruna (2011), states that education is a weapon to fight against poverty and human daily challenges. Oyekan (2004) asserted that no nation can tower beyond the level of her educational studies. Sarumi (2001), opined that a sustainably development of any nation's progress and development could only be guaranteed through functional education. Chukwu (2011), posits that in any nation, the educational sector is often considered as one of the most important social institutions for socio-economic, technological and scientific development, especially in the twenty first century, characterized by knowledge explosion the place of quality and functional education at all levels cannot be over-emphasized. Aderinoye (2002) maintains that acquisition of knowledge and education is a must for individuals in the society.

Erinsakin (2018) asserts that in Nigeria, the challenge to the educational system in the recent times has to do with the provision of quality education now and for future generations considering the challenge of few educational institutions, especially at tertiary level of education in the country. The recognition of this challenge informal implementation of different educational programmes to cater for the education of adults who were interested to either complete their initial lost education or acquire further knowledge for reason(s) that is/are personal individuals in the society.

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It can be deciphered that, globally, it has become clear that education must be an important part of all strategies for development. In the series of world conferences on education held between 1990 and 1996, the various agencies of the United Nations (UN) address the issues of education for all, the environment, human rights, population, social development, the status of women, human settlement and food scarcity (Maduewesi, 2005). Each of the conferences recognized that progress would be dependent on educated members of society transforming their life circumstances and gaining greater control over their lives. To achieve this change, citizenry requires new knowledge, skills and attitudes. This significant insight was highlighted by the Fifth International Conference on Adult Education (CONFINTEA) that adult learning is potentially a powerful force for promoting people-centered development. Education is a key to sustainable development in the Twenty first century (Sarumi, 2001).

Sarumi (2001), opines that learners do come for educational programmes for various personal reasons such as; economic, political, social etc. The motivational factors are not the same. This is the situations for the special needs learners. People with special needs are all over the places in all societies of the world. Within and outside different educational institutions of learning there are learners with special needs that require responses to their education. Obani (2004) special need learners may have learning or attention difficulties, intellectual; retardation, behavioural problem, physical and health related problems, disordered communication, hearing impaired and visually impaired etc. What this indicated is that disabilities are not barrier to educational aspirations.

Globally, today's attention has been given to the people that need special education, hence result into establishment of special needs Educational institutions for the category of the people in the society, coupled with giving them spaces and admission in many institutions of learning.

From the avalanche of studies on special needs learners or students, observably, much study have not been carried out on motivational factors of special needs students quest for tertiary education. This identified gap however, serves as a motivational factors for the researcher to carry out this study.

Statement of the Problem

Education is very imperative and synonymous with development in a holistic context. Therefore, this necessitated implementation of various educational programmes to cater for the educational needs of people with disabilities in the society. Education is a basic fundamental human rights as contained in UNESCO Declaration on Education as a fundamental right of individuals in the society' regardless of sex, religion, race, health status etc.

Hence, special need students are enrolling for different educational programmes based on their preference, interest and their educational needs. Some re-occurring questions that keep on lingering in the minds of people are:

1. What are the considerations of special needs students for enrolment in educational programme?
2. Are special needs students enrolment for education programme is for social values? It

was against this backdrop this study was carried out by the researchers.

Purpose of the Study

The study focused on motivational factors for enrolment of special needs students' quest for tertiary education for educational programmes. The purposes of the research were to;

1. determine whether special needs students quest for tertiary education is for economic reasons;
2. investigate special needs students desire for tertiary education is for occupational development; and
3. ascertain whether special needs students yearning for tertiary education is to acquire educational certificate

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study;

1. Does involvement of special needs students in educational programme for economic reason?
2. Does special needs students' involvement in educational programme centres on occupational development?
3. Are special needs students' participation in educational programme on the need to acquire further educational certificate?

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study were significant to stakeholders in education in the following ways;

1. The result of the study would establish whether, desire for social status enhancement informs special needs learners participation in educational programmes.

2. Moreover, findings of the study will also help to provide objective answers to reasons for involvement of special needs students on educational programmes.
3. Finally, the study will add to the extant literature in the area of the study, thus, becomes a good source of reference materials for the researcher, who will carry out study within the confine of the research area in future.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Erinsakin (2014) theory explain a relationship between two variables on events. Theory is formulated to explain predict and understand phenomena. A theory is an attempt to explain why and so to provide understanding. This study was therefore anchored on:

1. Cognitive Theory of Motivation (C.T.M)

According to Fagerbers Diallo (2002), cognitive theory of motivation emphasis the role of thought processes in bringing about motivation. The cognitive theory of motivation states that individuals do what they want to, based on their rational evaluation of the likely effects of the cause of action.

The Cognitive Theory of Motivation (CTM), stresses that the way in which individuals perceive the usefulness of a course of action from the internal rationalization of the possible outcome. the theory says that every action there must be a motive that precedes the action . for example, a study of adult literally learners in Senegal, concluded by Fagerberg Diallo (2002: 45-60), indication that adult leaner enrolled in the programme because they needed to be to read letter, apply their knowledge of calculation in everyday like and contribute more effectively to community development.

What is very important in this theory is that cognitive theory of motivation arises from individuals needs and this is justification for the selection and relevance of cognitive theory of motivation for the study. More so, that adult learners participation on educational programme arise on the need of usefulness of the programme for reasons.

Diagram showing Motivation Factor of Special Needs Students Participation in Tertiary Educational Programme

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Motivation

Motivation defines the generic term, motives, as "goal-directed behaviour ". He then divides this into the "unlearned, biogenic motives" which originate in the functioning of organic needs, and the "learned, sociogenic motives" which are acquired in the course of genetic

development of the individual, and the goals of which are derived from interpersonal experience.

The latter, or learned, motives are of primary concern herein.

Arshad (1993), defines motivation as "the dynamics of behaviour". In terms of its derivation, the word motive means to move, to activate. In this general sense, anything that initiates activity, whether external or internal, is motivating. In psychology, however, the terms motivation and motive refer to activation from within the organism. Thus motivated behaviour is internally activated, at least modified by, internal conditions. A motive, therefore, is some internal activation or modifier.

A similar definition of motive is presented by Sanford, "a motive is an energizing condition of the organism that serves as direct that organism toward a certain goal". Psychological motives are constructs used to account for the social or interpersonal behaviour of the individual. Such motives are more a product of the environment in which a person lives and less a product of the individual's organic nature.

Two authors have in recent years stressed the idea, consonant with but not explicitly supported by data, that human motives can be arranged in a hierarchy from stronger and lower at one end to weaker and higher at the other. Such an idea has a significance both for a theoretical and a practical approach to motivation and commands attention here. The hierarchy as originally described by Maslow is as follows:

1. The physiological needs, hunger, thirst, air etc.
2. The safety needs, the need for freedom from threat or danger, the need to ally oneself with the familiar and the secure

3. The belongingness and love needs, the need for affiliation, for belongingness, for acceptance
4. The esteem needs, the need for achievement, for strength, for competence, for reputation, for status or prestige.
5. The need for self-actualization, the need for self-fulfillment, to realize potentialities, to become what one is capable of becoming
6. Cognitive needs, the need to know and understand, curiosity, the need to understand the mysterious, the need to tackle the unknown
7. Esthetic needs, the need for symmetry, order, system and structure.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study, because not everybody in the study population could be covered. Therefore, data generated from the sample size was generalized on the entire study population. The study population comprised special needs students that were on educational programme in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria.

A total number of Two hundred (200) respondents constituted the sample size of the study. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the respondents from Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria.

The research instruments used was self-developed questionnaire by the researcher, entitled, "Questionnaire on Empirical Investigation on Motivational Factors of Special Needs Students Quest for Tertiary Education, Ondo State, Nigeria", fashioned on four likert rating scale

of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), rated on 4; 3; 2 and 1 points, respectively. The research instruments were two experts in Test and Measurement. The reliability of research instruments was done through, test retest method and 0.67 coefficient reliability obtained. Data collected on research question were analysed, using descriptive statistics frequency, counts, simple percentages and mean.

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Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 4.1 shows the various age groups of the respondents of the study and where they belong, 25% of the respondents were drawn from the age range of 18 to 25 years. Those within the age range of 26 to 35 years constituted 30% of the respondents. 36 to 45 years constituted 26% respondents, while the percentage that falls within the age group of 46 and above constituted 19% of the respondents. Therefore, what can be deciphered from the analysis above is that the respondents belong to different age groups.

Figure 4.2: Analysis of Distribution of the Respondents by Gender

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Figure 4.2 xrays the fact that male principals and vice-principals are more than female principals and vice-principals. Hence, from the analysis above, males constituted 40% of the respondents which was 40%, while the 60% are females.

The discrepancy in figure 4.2 in the percentages of female and male respondents further reiterates the fact the fact, women constitute the highest number of people in our society. Also that educational education develop individuals in the society to the fullest. This lends credence to the views of Okojie (2003 & 2008) and Ruiz (2007) that education is a strategy to empower individuals and develop the nation.

Presentation of Findings on Research Questions

Research Question One: Is my enrolment for educational programme for economic reason?

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Table 1: Showing frequency counts, simple percentages and mean (\bar{X}) on is my enrolment for educational programme for economic reason

S/N	Items	SD %	D %	A %	SA %	Mean	Remarks
7	Economic reasons made me enroll for educational programme	155 77.5	23 11.5	13 6.5	9 4.5	1.38	Rejected
8	My enrolment for the programme is not connected with economic reason	7 3.5	20 10	23 11.5	150 75	3.58	Accepted
9	Educational programme could enhance me financially	144 72	30 15	14 7	12 6	1.47	Rejected
10	The programme could not enhance my financial status	18 9	22 11	36 18	124 62	3.33	Accepted
Average Mean		324 40.5	95 11.8	86 10.7	295 36.8	2.4	Rejected

Table 1 above, shows the result on research question two. On item (7), 9 (4.5%); 13 (6.5%); 23 (11.5%) and 155 (77.5%) responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (8). 150 (75%); 23 (11.5%), 20 (10%) and 7 (3.5%) responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (9), 12 (6%); 14 (7%); 30 (15%) and 144 (72%) responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Finally, on item (10), the following responses were also obtained; 124 (62%); 36 (18%); 22 (11%) and 18 (9%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Research Question Two: Does special need students involvement on educational programmes centres on occupational development?

Table 2: Showing frequency counts, simple percentages and mean (\bar{X}) on does special needs students' involvement on educational programmes centres on occupational development

S/N	Items	SD %	D %	A %	SA %	Mean	Remarks
11	I registered for educational programme because I am jobless	130 65	30 15	22 11	18 9	1.64	Rejected
12	If I am not jobless, I would have register for the programme	120 60	40 20	20 10	20 10	1.44	Rejected
13	I need educational programme to update my grade level at my work place	148 74	32 16	14 7	6 3	1.7	Rejected
14	The nature of my work require no further educational programme	6 3	14 7	40 20	140 70	3.57	Accepted
Average Mean		404 50.5	116 14.5	96 12	184 23	2.0	Rejected

Table 2 above, presents the findings on research question three. On item (11), 18 (9%); 22 (11%); 30 (15%) and 130 (65%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (12), 20 (10%), 20 (10%), 40 (20%) and 120 (60%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (13), the following responses were obtained; 6 (3%); 14 (7%); 32 (16%) and 148 (74%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Finally, on item (14), the following responses were obtained; 140 (70%), 40 (20%); 14 (7%) and 6 (3%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Research Question Three: Are special needs students' involvement on educational programme on the need to acquire further educational certificate?

Table 3: Showing frequency counts, simple percentages and mean (\bar{X}) on are special needs students' involvement on educational programme on the need to acquire further educational certificate

S/N	Items	SD %	D %	A %	SA %	Mean	Remarks
15	My enrolment for educational programme is to have additional certificate	160 80	12 6	18 9	10 5	1.39	Rejected
16	My enrolment for the programme has nothing to do with acquisition of further educational certificate	12 6	16 8	10 5	162 81	3.61	Accepted
17	The programme could improve my occupational skills	141 70.5	23 11.5	20 10	16 8	1.55	Rejected
18	Despite enrolment for the programme, my occupational skills will not be improved	7 3.5	25 12.5	36 18	132 66	3.46	Accepted
Average Mean		320 40	76 9.5	84 10.5	320 40	2.5	Accepted

Table 3 presents the findings on research question four. On item (15), the following responses were obtained; 10 (5%); 18 (9%); 12 (6%) and 160 (80%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (16) 162 (81%); 10 (5%); 16 (8%) and 12 (6%) responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (17), 16 (8%); 20 (10% 23 (11.5%) and 141 (70.5%) responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Finally, on item (18), the following responses were obtained; 132 (66%); 36 (18%); 25 (12.5%) and 7 (3.5%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Research Question Four: Do I enroll for educational programme because of stipend giving to special needs students?

Table 4: Showing frequency counts, simple percentages and mean (\bar{X}) on do I enroll for educational programme because of stipend giving to special needs students.

S/N	Items	SD %	D %	A %	SA %	Mean	Remarks
19	My enrolment for educational programme is because of stipends	143 71.5	23 11.5	22 11	12 6	1.5	Rejected
20	I enrolled for the programme not because of the stipend giving to special needs students	5 7.5	20 10	32 16	133 66.5	3.4	Accepted
21	My enrolment for educational programme if far from any incentive giving to special needs students	146 73	23 11.5	18 9	13 6.5	1.4	Rejected
22	Without any incentive, I still have interest in educational programme	14 7	17 8.5	29 14.5	140 70	3.4	Accepted
Average Mean		318 39.7	83 10.3	101 12.6	298 37.2	2.4	Rejected

Table 5 above, shows the results on research question five. On item (19), the following responses were obtained; 12 (6%); 22 (11%); 23 (11.5%) and 143 (71.5%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (20), 133 (66.5%); 32 (16%); 20 (10%) and 15 (7.5%) responses were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (21), the following responses were obtained: 13 (6.5%); 18 (9%); 23 (11.5%) and 146 (73%) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Finally on item (22), 140 (70%); 29 (14.5%); 17 (8.5%) and 14 (7%) responses were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Discussion of Findings

The finding on research question one states that the average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is greater than the mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.4$), thus portends that special needs

students participation in educational programme have no positive relationship with economic factors. The result negates the opinion of many academic that economic factor is one of those considerations by people's that result into their educational programmes.

Moreover, the result on research question two shows that the average of rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is not greater than or lesser than the average of rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$). This means that adult learners participation in educational programme is for occupational development. This aligns with the opinion of Okemakinde and Erinsakin (2023), that the need to acquire relevant skills for occupation development makes many learners to enroll for educational programme

Furthermore, the result on research question three shows that, the average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is not greater than the mean of average of rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$), also thus, shows that adults' enrolment for educational programme is premised on the desire for educational certificate. This agree with the opinion of Akpan (2001) that enrolment of many learners, special needs students, inclusively for educational programme is due to the desire to acquire for educational certificate.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research, conclusion were made that economic reasons and the desire to achieve acquire certificate and occupational development in order to cope with the demand and dynamic nature of work or job in the 21st century informs the quest for special needs quest for tertiary education in Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

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Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were made;

1. Government should sensitize the special needs students on their needs to acquire functional educational programme in Nigeria
2. Motivations in various forms should be giving to the special needs students of any educational programme in Nigeria.
3. Education programme should be made more accessible to the special needs students in the society.
4. Special needs students' needs for educational programme should be provided by government.
5. Educational programme for special needs students should take their peculiarities into consideration.
6. Educational programme for adult learners should be made comfortable for them in terms of accessibility, cost and time conveniency etc.

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